

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SPATIAL PATTERNS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVING LOCAL GOVERNANCE IN BULGARIA

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Abstract

This paper presents several issues related to the spatial planning problems that arise as a demographic situation consequence. The paper outlines the general Bulgarian municipal spatial planning problems which are divided into urban and rural. The primary issues arise in rural municipalities, where the majority of problem groups can be found. The article presents a methodological approach for the territory analysis and assessment, employing traditional approaches and methods. The paper presents a series of conclusions and recommendations. The text presents a model for identifying differences in national legislation on social security, with particular reference to the distinctive characteristics of municipal development in Bulgaria. In conclusion, the authors put forth a series of measures and policies designed to have a positive impact on the municipalities' development.

Keywords: municipality, development, services, public management, space, areal

Introduction

Access to public services is a fundamental right of every citizen. It is largely provided by local authorities. It is reasonable to discuss municipal policy in terms of the quality of life of the population and the necessity for effective spatial planning and efficient public management. The state legislature establishes the overarching principles that guide the formulation of the primary spatial policy objectives and principles. In this regard, it is essential to develop a spatial planning policy that the territory should not be regarded as a mere mechanical aggregation of landed properties, but rather as a unified and indivisible entity, created by nature and shaped and inherited from history, on which landed properties of diverse types and sizes are formed and transformed over time to facilitate the functioning of individual and collective life activities and to respond to their constantly evolving development needs. Consequently, public management influences landed property utilization, conservation, and advancement. This encompasses the territory's functional, structural, and communicative organization and infrastructural provision. Consequently, the public and private investment initiatives implementation rise to the formation of a complex spatial environment with specific qualities. In this context, spatial and territorial planning has a direct impact on the socio-economic development of the national territory, while urban planning, in terms of settlements and settlement formations, plays a pivotal role. It is the principal instrument through which local authorities facilitate the landowners' entrepreneurial initiatives and investment intentions, regulating their compliance with the permanent purpose and specific characteristics of the land and providing them with infrastructure. In doing so, they "discipline" investments

in the name of and by the common and lasting interests of the respective territorial community. In Bulgaria, there are 266 municipalities. 215 are rural municipalities.

1. Population and Settlement States and Public Governance

One of the most significant reasons for the high population mobility observed in the twenty-first century is the emergence of regional disparities, particularly in terms of changes in living standards. Municipal spatial planning policy is developed by certain generally applicable principles and is based on an assessment of the existing situation in the municipality and the individual settlements [1]. This assessment is conducted to identify the objectives and priorities of the policy, as well as to analyze the factors that will influence the achievement of the objectives during the period of its implementation. Furthermore, the analysis should include an estimation of the resources that will be available for the implementation of spatial planning measures. The spatial development policy's principal substantive element is the guidelines for the development of the functional and structural components of the municipal territory and the individual settlements, together with the tasks to be carried out to implement the guidelines or achieve the objectives. The content of each municipal spatial development policy should be tailored to the specific characteristics of the municipality concerned. About this matter, it is evident that the municipalities in our country exhibit a considerable degree of diversity. This is evident from their respective sizes, the number of inhabitants, topography, the urbanization degree, economic structure, and other activities, and the rank and development of their respective infra-

structure [2]. The challenges facing Bulgarian municipalities are becoming increasingly complex. Rather than addressing local issues, the number of municipalities in a depressed state is increasing [2]. Conversely, the population's living standard is also contingent upon the availability of employment and the remuneration received, which must be sufficient to enable residents to flourish within their local environment. For instance, despite the observed decline in the population in the fourth quarter of 2023, the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) produced. The total value of the indicator was BGN 5,184,860,000 at current prices, according to the National Statistical Institute (NSI). The per capita value of the indicator was BGN 8,053. At the average exchange rate for the quarter of BGN 1.82 per USD 1, GDP amounted to USD 28,480,000,000 or USD 4,424 per capita. Converted into euros, GDP is EUR 26,510 million, with EUR 4,118 per capita. The total number of employed persons in the fourth quarter of 2023 is 2,920.6 thousand, of which 1,556.5 thousand are men and 1,364.1 thousand are women. In comparison, to the fourth quarter of 2022, the number of employees decreased by 2.0% for the entire population, with a 1.6% decline for men and a 2.5% reduction for women. The proportion of employed individuals aged 15 and over was 53.1%, 59.6% for men, and 47.2% for women. The number of unemployed individuals in the fourth quarter of 2023 was 128.6 thousand. 68.9 thousand (53.6%) were men, and 59.7 thousand (46.4%) were women. In comparison, to the fourth quarter of 2022, the number of unemployed individuals increased by 13.0 thousand, representing an increase of 11.2%. The unemployment rate is 4.2% (compared to 3.7% in the fourth quarter of 2022), with no significant difference between the sexes [5]. The analysis of major centers reveals that the gravitational field of the capital is particularly strong, given the administrative and economic potential that is concentrated in it. However, Bulgaria is developing through a monocentric model, which, although it creates large territorial and demographic imbalances, is a necessary consequence of the country's historical development. Consequently, the migration flow is strongly oriented towards Sofia. The distance between Sofia and Plovdiv is 120 km, with the gravity zone in favor of Sofia. Sofia's influence extends only 50 km from Plovdiv, although Plovdiv is the second-largest city in Bulgaria. This indicates that Plovdiv is a center of attraction for population movement towards it within a 50 km radius. Similarly, the gravity zones of Sofia and Blagoevgrad intersect 39 km from the smaller regional city. This represents a significant challenge for the development of Southwest Bulgaria. This indicates that Plovdiv is a focal point for population movement within a 50 km radius. Similarly, the gravity zones of Sofia and Blagoevgrad intersect 39 km from the smaller

regional city. This is a significant challenge for the development of Southwest Bulgaria. The analysis also indicates that Sofia exerts a gravitational influence on Pleven at a distance of 162 km; Ruse exerts a gravitational influence on Varna at a distance of 150 km (i.e. Varna has a significant advantage over Ruse); Sofia exerts a gravitational influence on V. Tarnovo at a distance of 83 km from the capital; for Sofia exerts a gravitational influence on Varna, the gravitational field of the capital ends 153 km before the sea town. The concept of zones of gravity or regional economic influence can be employed to inform the formulation of national and local policies for the development of local systems at different territorial levels: national, regional, district, and zonal [3]. The study results can also be used to justify the Bulgarian state regionalization and territorial administrative reform, to justify the policy, to make more efficient use of structural funds, and to ensure territorial cohesion at the level of municipalities.

2. Powers and competencies of the management bodies of the municipalities

In the context of local self-government, in the municipality, in particular, the mayor is responsible for managerial functions, while the municipal council is vested with exclusive normative functions. In this capacity, municipal government can act as a regulator within the local business and social environment. A team of authors has conducted an in-depth analysis of the role and significance of municipalities, with a particular focus on public governance, including local government and regional politics, municipal self-governance, and the municipal development planning process [4]. At the municipal level, various processes are achieved by specialists with expertise in urban planning and architecture, geography, economics, sociology, and heritage conservation. The work method is complex, as it once relied on an analytical plan designed to evaluate legislative changes in the settlement system in Bulgaria. Conversely, the socio-economic development of municipalities is contingent upon their actual evolution in terms of economic, social, and cultural infrastructure, as well as conceptual and prospective considerations about the restructuring or reorganization of the settlement system [4]. To achieve high efficiency in the functioning of local governments, it would be beneficial to consider improvements to the services, administration, and applied regulations. In this context, it is possible to consider the local regulations' potential optimization, which could improve results in the business environment. This thesis is supported by the respondents' responses regarding the potential for reducing local-level regulations. The figure indicates that 269 respondents expressed a positive view of the potential for reducing regulations, while 48 respondents provided a negative response to this question.

Figure 1 Should local regulations be reduced?

The survey revealed that 127 respondents, representing the majority of the sample, perceived the level of administrative services to be average. One hundred individuals rated municipal services at a low level. The survey revealed that 73 respondents were satisfied with the administrative quality of municipalities. A total of 50 respondents indicated that the quality of administrative services was satisfactory, while 33 respondents rated it as very low (Figure 1). The results demonstrate the efficiency of local governments in their functioning. The quality of administrative services impacts the tangible conditions created for the population to work and live in an area, do business, and attract, and retain residents [6]. The quality of administrative services is indicative of how processes are managed within the administration itself and its territory. As previously indicated, a significant proportion of the respondents indicated that they did not consider the level of services provided by the municipalities to be high. This indicates a need for continuous monitoring of local authorities, with the implementation of policies and measures designed to enhance administrative processes and, in turn, facilitate the creation of conducive conditions for business, work, and living.

3. Methods of the municipal governance approach

A detailed examination of the outcomes of the subsequent stages is conducted. Firstly, it is necessary to identify the principal territorial, demographic, economic, and social services of each of these regions/areas. To go further national, regional, and municipal strategic documents were utilized. The labor market dependencies identification specific to the region is also a key aspect of this analysis. The analysis is based on the business and labor force survey results conducted within Bulgaria and our regions. The study framework also includes a comparative analysis considering the positive and negative influences of the external and internal environment for each region/municipality separately for 2021-2014. In terms of methodology, a summary of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats is presented in tabular form. The comparative analysis encompasses all factors that facilitate or impede municipal integration. The subsequent step is to draw conclusions and formulate recommendations. The activity proceeds in the following sequence, conducted

on the spot. Afterward, differences in national social security legislation, laws, fiscal levels, wage levels, and other factors are identified that affect cross-border integration [7]. It is becoming increasingly important to study the cross-border labor market mobility level in the selected cross-border regions and the main obstacles and barriers that occur in the state border regions.

4. Framework and feature in the formation of the gravity field of the municipality

The analysis of some major centers reveals that the gravitational field of the capital is strong, given the administrative and economic potential concentration. Unfortunately, Bulgaria has a monocentric development model creating significant territorial and demographic imbalances. Consequently, the migration flow is strongly biased towards Sofia. The distance between Sofia and Plovdiv is 120 km, with Sofia enjoying a gravity zone advantage. Despite Plovdiv being the second largest city in Bulgaria, its influence is limited to a radius of only 50 km from Sofia. This implies that Plovdiv is a focal point for population migration within a 50-kilometre radius. Similarly, the gravity zones of Sofia and Blagoevgrad intersect 39 km from the smaller regional city. This represents a significant challenge for the development of Southwest Bulgaria. The analysis also indicates that Sofia exerts a gravitational influence on Pleven, with a distance of 162 km; Ruse-Varna, with a distance of 150 km (i.e. Varna enjoys a significant advantage over Ruse); Sofia-V. Tarnovo, with a boundary at 83 km from the capital; and Sofia-Varna, with the gravitational field of the capital reaching 153 km before the sea town. To achieve optimal efficiency in the functioning of local authorities, it would be beneficial to consider improvements to the service, administration, and regulations that are currently in place. In this context, we consider the possibility of experimenting with local regulations, which could potentially lead to a more restrictive business environment. This thesis is supported by the respondents' responses regarding the potential for reducing regulations at the local level. The figure indicates that 269 respondents expressed a positive view of the potential for reducing regulations, while 48 respondents provided a negative response to this question.

Figure 2 What is the quality level of administrative services in municipalities?

The survey revealed that 127 respondents, representing the majority of the sample, perceived the level of administrative services to be average. One hundred individuals rated municipal services at a low level. The survey revealed that 73 respondents were satisfied with the administrative quality of municipalities. A total of 50 respondents indicated that the quality of administrative services was satisfactory, while 33 respondents rated it as very low (Figure 2). These findings indicate the efficiency of local governments in their functioning. The quality of administrative services has a direct impact on the creation of tangible conditions for the population to work and live, engage in business activities, and attract and retain local populations. The quality of administrative services is indicative of how processes are managed within the administration itself and its territory. As previously indicated, a significant proportion of the respondents rated the quality of municipal services as unsatisfactory [8]. Consequently,

local authorities must be subject to constant monitoring, with policies and measures implemented to enhance administrative processes and facilitate the formation of conducive conditions for business, work, and living. Modern municipal authorities are increasingly empowered, yet financial resources remain a significant challenge. Resources are of the utmost importance, as they are the foundation upon which municipalities can fulfill their daily activities and meet the population needs within their territory. Modern municipalities perform a wide range of functions including social, economic, administrative, territorial, and urban planning.

The primary objective of any municipality is to create the requisite socio-economic conditions for development and social welfare. One of the most effective ways of achieving this is through the municipality's role as a regulator of social and economic processes within its territory.

Figure 3 Main problems in municipalities.

Although municipalities are supposed to be the drivers of socio-economic processes within their administrative territory, they fail to exercise their powers effectively and fully. This conclusion is reached by analyzing the results of the responses on the main problems in the municipalities (Figure 3). The largest number of respondents 93 considered infrastructure to be the main problem facing municipal development. The respondents who identified the following as the main problems in the municipalities are almost equally distributed: demographic, administrative, and economic (63, 55, and 52 respondents respectively). According to 27 respondents, social problems are essential for the development of municipalities. 9 out of all respondents identified transport problems as the leading problem in their municipality. And 18 persons indicated other problems that were not specifically identified. Here we should bear in mind the fact that depending on the municipality's size, and the location the problems that exist are different. However, this relationship has not been explored in this study.

Local self-government automatically determines the autonomy of the municipal government. At the same time, autonomy is directly related to the ability of

the municipality to accumulate and spend financial resources. Through local finance and municipal fiscal policy, each municipality stimulates economic, demographic, and social development within the territory. In fact, within the municipality's administrative boundaries are located several economic entities that produce gross product [9]. The made and realized output levels of services determine the municipality's living standard, income level, population purchasing power, and private and foreign direct investment. In this sense, it is normal that a large part of the tax revenues and profits of firms remain in the municipalities. In Sweden, for example, about 50% of personal taxes remain in the city, with more than half of the accumulated funds in the state budget being spent by municipal authorities.

In the figure, we can see how municipal spending is distributed about the gross domestic product and the average population of the countries in the European Union. It is noteworthy that in rich European countries municipalities have more resources. In terms of population, the municipalities are comparable, including the Bulgarian ones, but there are also large differences in the average number across countries.

Table 1

Statistical information on territorial imbalances and municipal spending relative to countries (2022).

State	State governance level number	Average population number in the municipality	Municipal expenditure of GDP (%)
Austria	3	3568	7.8
Belgium	4	18676	7.0
Hurvatia	3	7932	6.2
Cyprus	2	2211	4.8
Czech Republic	3	1685	5.7
England	3	144342	9.63
France	4	1768	7.0
Allemania	4	7265	7.2
Greece	3	34800	3.5
Hungary	3	3654	7.8
Ireland	2	40088	3.6
Italy	3	7493	5.3
Latvia	2	17395	10.8
Lithuania	2	48873	6,4
Netherlands	3	40833	7.5
Poland	4	15543	10.0
Portugal	2	34293	6.1
Rumania	3	6260	7.0
Slovak Republic	3	1780	3.6
Slovenia	2	9730	5.3
Spain	4	5651	4.3
Sweden	3	32483	15.6

Regional policy is essentially the prerogative of the state. In essence, it can also be called investment policy. However, the municipality is also actively involved in the business environment and creating jobs by implementing this type of policy. The investment process is important for creating a favorable. The problems in different municipalities are too diverse (as Figure 3 makes clear) for the state to implement a sufficiently effective and efficient policy to solve them. Therefore, the municipality's powers and the autonomy

degree should correspond to the available financial resources in the municipal budget. The municipality has an important role to play in terms of regulating labor market mobility and addressing social inequalities, as well as stimulating fertility. Therefore, the municipality must be a social and economic entrepreneur.

Considering the municipality as a social regulator and entrepreneur is a contemporary role that must create certain conditions in territorial communities. In

this direction, municipalities should form policies and implement instruments to stimulate social entrepreneurship. This can be done through funding social activities, communities, and business initiatives. This means providing grants for businesses to create jobs; activities related to helping disadvantaged people; funding micro-projects, etc. The municipality can also build and develop sustainable networks of social and economic actors [10]. These are the government, municipalities, some companies, social institutions, and NGOs. The third tool includes the creation of infrastructure and social hubs through which to offer business ideas, basic services for start-ups, the creation of foundations with shared governance, the online advice provision for the start-ups' development, etc.

There is a direct relationship between land use, land development, zoning of the community, and its economic development. In this sense, it is of particular importance that the urbanization of the territory is planned and controlled, rather than happening spontaneously without the municipality's involvement. A good example of good municipal planning is Rakovski. Years ago, an industrial zone was built within the municipality with the necessary communication and infrastructure connectivity, infrastructure, various buildings depending on the activities, and an appropriate policy to attract foreign direct investment and establish companies there. As a result, the municipality of Rakovski is socio-economically and demographically developed, supporting the existence of the surrounding settlements.

5. Guidelines for municipal spatial planning policy in rural areas

The content guidelines are the core of the municipal spatial planning policy as they operationalize its objectives by structural elements and vital systems. Just as the objectives and guidelines, or the related tasks are determined depending on the revealed specific problems of the territory and by the universal principles of modern Western European spatial planning [11]. The practice in our country over the last ten years gives grounds to recommend that the guidelines be formulated taking into account (taking into account) the principle requirements set out below. Conducting a line of balanced development and spatial organization of the entire territory of the municipality, which means:

- the rational and full use in situ of the natural and anthropogenic resources available in the different parts of the territory;
- the achievement and maintenance of an equitable quality settlement environment offering equal access to employment opportunities, knowledge, cultural assets, and basic services;
- achieving spatially continuous natural areas that provide people with opportunities for daily contact with the natural environment within a 10-15 minute transport isochrones;
- the full development of transport and infrastructure networks and modern means of decentralized engineering and technical provision, which offer equivalent opportunities for access to and from all inhabited parts of the municipality to high

levels of transport communications and an equivalent level of amenity.

About the structure of land use and the territorial development of settlements and other urbanized areas at the municipal level, to counteract the trend, which has increased in recent years, of agricultural land being used for development, or at least to prevent this from happening at the expense of high-category agricultural land. It should also be borne in mind that hypertrophied urban sprawl, such as that which is occurring in certain parts of the country, imposes significant additional costs on the development and operation of the territory for decades to come [12].

Two main problems need to be addressed in particular in the guidelines related to territorial and field provision of economic activities. The first is the creation of conditions for the penetration of such activities of a harmless production and service nature into residential areas not to take place randomly and spontaneously, i.e. at the expense of the qualities of the residential environment and to the detriment of the activities themselves, but in an orderly manner by certain urban planning principles. The second is the urgent urban restructuring of existing production zones and the suitable site creation for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Notwithstanding the continued absence of a national housing policy, the guidance on housing development should provide:

- the achievement of a variety of housing environments in different parts of towns and cities, as a condition for free choice of living arrangements;
- conditions for the implementation of compact mass housing operations, affordable to low-income families, and for social housing for the needs of disadvantaged categories - the disabled, single mothers, minority groups;
- conditions for the development of high-category housing in urban and suburban environments;
- a clear distinction between the roles of the municipality and the private sector in housing construction: public investment - only for infrastructure and partly for land provision, private investment - for housing construction and participation in infrastructure building.

Due to the difficulties of terrain provision for large-scale development of public landscaped areas, it is essential to formulate effective measures to protect the existing ones from all kinds of invasions and to promote a high degree of landscaping on residential and non-residential regulated land. At the same time, in cases where the municipality has a significant land reserve, it is desirable to allocate it to landscaping needs as a priority.

An important requirement is that, in the context of a decline in the construction of public services, opportunities for further town center systems development should not be allowed to be compromised. Moreover, it is important to provide land opportunities for the construction of new, complex, and specialized centers for the development of various forms of knowledge is a significant development., such as will be realized in a future phase with cooperative public

and private investment. An example of this is the complex shopping and service centers that will inevitably arise in the process of concentrating commercial activity and integrating it with other forms of service.

Regarding social infrastructure development, it is necessary to preserve the land earmarked. But not used for schools to create conditions for single-sex education. In this case, the requirement of proximity to the place of residence remains valid only for primary schools, and for the upper course, available municipal land elsewhere should be used and land reserved on the periphery of towns [13]. When existing housing estates are redeveloped, it is important to consider the land for children to play. Development measures for environmental protection should be directed in two directions: preventive and compensatory, which can be implemented by public management to achieve sustainable development of regions and efficiency on the part of institutions and organizations.

At the regional level, the preventive measures include the landscape planning approach application and the transport and infrastructure communications implementation with a minimum disturbance to the natural environment. At the settlement level, the activity and construction load on individual parts of the territory should be limited to the permissible limits for air pollution and energy efficiency. Of the compensatory measures, the emphasis should be on the green areas development (at least in the peri-urban area), protection from traffic noise, and efficient evacuation and waste treatment.

In the development of the urban communication and transport system, priority should be given to the mass public transport system, the improvement of the street network in the short and medium term should be based primarily on existing routes, maximizing the connectivity of the network, and leaving room for future more radical solutions. Particular attention should be paid to parking and stationing issues.

Special attention should be paid to the connection with the regional and local transport system regarding the municipalities through whose territory the European transport and infrastructure corridors routes are planned to pass, as well as the realization of the development potential they carry [14].

When defining the guidelines for engineering and technical infrastructure systems development it is important to consider the preconditioning and limiting the importance of territories' urbanization reconstruction and intensification (respectively, for the absorption of new territories). These factors are planned interdependently. It is essential to focus efforts on overcoming the lag in the construction of sanitation in urbanized areas regarding their water supply and future synchronous development. Particular attention should be paid to telecommunications development to master the opportunities that information and communication technologies will offer for radically improving the spatial organization of work activities, habitation, and services. According to the specific conditions of the municipalities concerned, the scope of municipal spatial planning policies should include

specialized guidelines on the spatial planning problems of specific areas - protected areas, areas with cultural heritage sites, coasts, and water areas, and settlements with particular functions. It is also necessary to outline clear guidelines for the management improvement of the spatial planning process, including the construction of a modern computerized information system, the programming of public investments, the streamlining of maintenance procedures, and technical equipment, and the strengthening of the technical services. In this sense, the guidelines, and the tasks must be prioritized. Here again, one of the main criteria for determining priority must be to serve more than one objective or guideline. This is also likely to be the case at lower levels of regional planning. In any case, the municipal spatial planning policy should build on the municipal and regional development plans, developing the trends set out in them for prospective development in the longer term. At the same time, if these trends are found to be at odds with the requirements for balanced and sustainable spatial organization and planning, it should make the contradictions explicit to take procedural action to overcome them.

6. Implementation of specialized municipal policies

Given the intricate nature of the subject matter, the municipality's rural policy is comprehensive in scope. This enables a connection with the regional development policy to facilitate optimal socio-economic development. Furthermore, the municipal spatial planning policy should be integrated with several other municipal specialized policy programs that address important spheres of activity with spatial dimensions. In this context, we are discussing two-way links of mutual conditionality. This is primarily the municipal environmental policy that each municipality must formulate and implement by the Environmental Protection Act and other environmental laws. The interconnection between the two policies is important, as it facilitates the transition towards integrated spatial and environmental planning, which is becoming increasingly prevalent in advanced countries. This approach ensures that environmental considerations are integrated into spatial planning decisions from the outset of the planning process. Secondly, there is a link with municipal policy. The important is the municipal energy efficiency program assigned to municipalities by the Energy and Energy Efficiency Act. Such programs are already in place and implemented by the municipalities that are members of the Ecoenergy Municipal Energy Efficiency Network. The links are primarily oriented toward measures implementation designed to enhance the energy efficiency of the building stock and utility systems. Thirdly, it is important to highlight the close relationship between spatial planning policy and municipal housing policy. Unfortunately, for a considerable period, the absence of a national housing policy and a corresponding legislative framework has made it virtually impossible for even the largest municipalities with the most acute housing problems to formulate their housing policies. Furthermore, there is a significant link with another currently non-existent municipal policy: land policy. In

all developed countries, the importance of municipal policy is evident.

Furthermore, there is a notable correlation with another municipal policy that is currently absent, namely land policy. In all developed countries, where the significance of municipal land as a primary source of municipal development has long been recognized and legally regulated, each municipality has its land policy, which is typically spatially oriented. Within this framework, municipalities are involved in municipal land reserve formation, participate in certain cases as economic entities in the land market, and ultimately oversee the spatial planning process. Although there is currently no legal framework for such policy formation in our country, it would be prudent to attempt to establish one within the context of the existing legislation. This would involve identifying projects that would encourage the implementation of effective regional development.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is recommended that efforts be made to optimize and develop rural areas through the municipal spatial planning policies implementation. In our case, the mountain policy and strategy implementation is essential to support the principles and measures of sustainable development of the mountain environment, by the examples set by countries within the European Union. It is recommended that the government give particular consideration to the strategy formulation to support mountain regions and to harmonise with European principles, to ensure the balanced development of mountain areas. The anticipated outcomes of implementing a mountainous region's sustainable development strategy include the more efficient utilization of natural resources, the advancement of agro-tourism and rural tourism, the production of distinctive local brand goods that uphold tradition, a bilateral and international collaboration for mountain development, and the modernization of infrastructure.

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